

EXPLICIT ASSESSMENT OF THE FORCED VIBRATION OF MULTI-CRACKED BEAMS WITH UNCERTAIN DAMAGE INTENSITY

F. Cannizzaro¹, N. Impollonia¹, G. Cocuzza Avellino¹, S. Caddemi¹, I. Calio¹

¹ Department of Civil Engineering and Architecture, University of Catania, via S. Sofia 64,
95123 Catania, (Italy)

francesco.cannizzaro@dica.unict.it, nimpo@unict.it, giuseppe.cocuzzaavellino@unict.it, salvatore.caddemi@unict.it, ivo.calio@unict.it

Keywords: Dynamic response, generalised functions, concentrated damage, explicit solution, uncertainty.

Abstract. *Damage in beams can strongly affect their dynamic properties and consequently their response. On the other hand, the correct evaluation of the damage intensity is a problem of difficult solution. For these reasons, exploring the variability of the dynamic response in damaged beams considering the damage intensities as uncertain parameter is a useful contribution to assess the safety of structures. Classic approaches require to treat damage as concentrated rotational springs, where continuity conditions have to be enforced, and to perform re-analyses varying the damage intensities in a desired range. In this paper, two main improvements to this procedure are provided. The first contribution is the use of an efficient solution which employs generalised functions to compute the dynamic properties of a damaged beam for a limited number of damage configurations; such a method avoids the enforcement of continuity conditions at the cracked sections. Then, an explicit continuous expression of such dynamic properties as a function of the damage intensities is proposed by employing the Sherman and Morrison formula. The proposed explicit approach is verified and applied for the evaluation of the dynamic properties of damaged beams; then, via modal superposition, the variability of the response associated to time histories is assessed as well as frequency-response curves for single and multi-cracked beams subjected to forced vibrations.*

1 INTRODUCTION

When the governing parameters of a structural problem are deterministic the response is deterministic as well. Nevertheless, it is widely accepted that uncertainties in the mechanical properties or in the loads acting on a structure strongly affect the expected response. This concept is embedded in most of the structural codes [1] adopted by practitioners, to assure a reasonable safety factor in the structural design and assessment.

This paper tries to handle the presence of uncertainties in beam-like structures. In particular, the focus is in the presence of damage, which is one of the most dangerous aspects for the safety of structures. Damage can occur in structures in a diffused or concentrated pattern. In presence of an early detection, damage can be approximately considered concentrated; for the latter reason a reliable approach to model the presence of damage in a structure is the so called equivalent rotational hinge model [2], which corresponds to connect in the damaged section the two sides of the beam with a rotational spring whose stiffness can be related to the crack depth according to different models [3]. Here, the presence of the internal rotational springs is treated by means of a distributional approach rather than enforcing continuity conditions at the cracked sections. The mentioned employed approach, which makes use of generalized functions to treat the singularities, allows to infer closed form solutions as a function of the boundary conditions only irrespectively of the number of along-axis cracks and proved to be effective in many static and dynamic problems [4][5]. However, the role of uncertainties was never explored by means of this solving strategy.

Uncertainties can be effectively modelled according to different strategies, namely a classical probabilistic approach [6], a fuzzy logic [7], or adopting the interval analysis, based on the assumption that an uncertain parameter can vary within a given range, without assuming any hypothesis on the probability content and aiming at inferring the bounds of a response parameter [8].

In this paper, beam structures, assumed as continuous Euler-Bernoulli models, are treated by making use of the generalized approach previously mentioned [4] to model the presence of concentrated cracks, considering their location as deterministic and introducing a model of uncertainty for the crack severities. The main modal parameters (frequencies, generalized masses and load terms in case of forced vibrations), are then approximated with a simple but effective explicit expression, whose reliability is duly verified. Once the main modal parameters are at hand in an explicit form, the forced vibrations of cracked beams are inferred as a function of uncertain crack depths, and the response surface is computed in a simplified manner. This explicit solution can be both employed to assess the response variability in direct problems and for inverse problem purposes. Here the dynamics of damaged beams with uncertain severity subjected to forced vibrations is explored. In particular, both time and frequency domain analyses are performed. In spite of the reduction of the needed computational effort for the parametric analysis with respect to a classic approach, it is shown how the proposed procedure is able to reproduce the bounds of the response otherwise to be computed according to an exact re-analysis. Remarkably, the proposed procedure is able to account for non-monotonic relationship between input and output variables and the procedure succeeds even when convex analysis [9] or other simplified procedures can fail for the treated problem.

2 THE GOVERNING EQUATIONS OF THE FORCED VIBRATION OF MULTI-CRACKED BEAMS

The computation of the forced vibrations of beam-like structures usually requires the employment of FE models or the adoption of continuous approaches. In presence of singularities, such as damage, FE models require the use of additional nodes and continuous approaches usually

employ the enforcement of continuity conditions at the discontinuous sections; in both cases the computational burden significantly increases with the number of damaged sections. In order to keep low the required computational demand to compute the forced vibration of cracked beams a convenient approach is here employed [10] and briefly recalled.

This strategy, which belongs to the framework of continuous approaches, mathematically treats the discontinuities by means of generalized functions, thus avoiding the enforcement of continuity conditions at the cracked sections and leads to a solution which depends on four boundary conditions only, irrespectively of the number of cracked sections. In particular, the dimensionless governing equation of the vibration of a multi-cracked Euler-Bernoulli beam, Figure 1, can be expressed as follows

$$u^{IV}(\xi, t) + \frac{mL^4}{E_o I_o} \ddot{u}(\xi, t) = \sum_{i=1}^n \Delta u'(\xi_i, t) \delta''(\xi - \xi_i) + q(\xi, t) \quad (1)$$

with t time variable and being $\xi = x/L$ the normalized abscissa (where L represents the beam length), $u(\xi, t) = v(x, t)/L$ the normalized deflection function, m the distributed mass, $E_o I_o$ the

bending stiffness of the beam, $q(\xi, t) = \frac{\bar{q}(x, t)L^3}{E_o I_o}$ the normalized transversal load, and ξ_i

($i=1, \dots, n$) are the normalized abscissae of the n cracked sections. $\delta(\bullet)$ is the well-known Dirac's delta distribution, and the superimposed dot and the apex indicate temporal and spatial differentiations, respectively. The jump rotations $\Delta u'(\xi_i, t)$ at the cracked sections can be related to the crack intensities, according to a classic equivalent hinge approach, to the dimensionless crack compliance $\lambda_i = \frac{E_o I_o}{K_i L}$ (where K_i is the stiffness of the equivalent rotational hinge), as follows

$$\Delta u'(\xi_i, t) = \lambda_i u''(\xi_i, t) \quad (2)$$

Figure 1: Multi-cracked beam subjected to an external transversal load

The damage compliance parameters, which can be easily related to the damage severities as in [11], can be conveniently collected in the vector $\lambda = [\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_i, \dots, \lambda_n]$.

The eigenproperties associated to Eq. (1) have already been inferred in closed form in [10]. In particular, the generic p -th mode shape ϕ_p , considering the explicit dependency on the crack compliance vector λ , can be expressed as follows:

$$\phi_p(\xi; \lambda) = \sum_{j=1}^4 C_{j,p}(\lambda) f_{j,p}(\xi; \lambda) \quad (3)$$

where $C_{j,p}(\lambda)$ represent the integration constants,

$$f_{j,p}(\xi; \lambda) = h_{j,p}(\xi; \lambda) + \sum_{k=1}^n \bar{h}_k(\xi; \lambda) \lambda_k f_{j,p}''(\xi; \lambda) \quad , \quad j=1, \dots, 4 \quad (4)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} h_{1,p}(\xi; \lambda) &= \sin \alpha_p \xi; & h_{2,p}(\xi; \lambda) &= \cos \alpha_p \xi; & h_{3,p}(\xi; \lambda) &= \sinh \alpha_p \xi; & h_{4,p}(\xi; \lambda) &= \cosh \alpha_p \xi; \\ \bar{h}_{i,p}(\xi; \lambda) &= \frac{1}{2\alpha_p} \left[\sin \alpha_p (\xi - \xi_i) + \sinh \alpha_p (\xi - \xi_i) \right] U(\xi - \xi_i) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

being $\alpha_p^4 = \omega_p^2 \frac{mL^4}{EI}$ the p -th frequency parameter depending on the boundary conditions of the beam and on its damage configuration.

The generic response of the beam at a desired abscissa ξ_r , can be expressed via modal superposition as:

$$r(\xi_r, t; \lambda) \cong \sum_{p=1}^{n_m} \phi_p^k(\xi_r; \lambda) z_p(t) \quad (6)$$

being $z_p(t)$, $p=1, \dots, \infty$ the modal coordinates and n_m the number of modes accounted in the solution. k represents the order of the derivative associated to the desired response $r(\xi_r, t; \lambda)$; in particular, the response in terms of deflection ($k=0$), rotation ($k=1$), bending moment ($k=2$), shear force ($k=3$) can be inferred. By replacing the modal superposition in the governing equation, and exploiting the orthogonality properties, the problem can be uncoupled leading to the following differential equations:

$$\ddot{z}_p(t) + 2\zeta_p \omega_p(\lambda) \dot{z}_p(t) + \omega_p^2(\lambda) z_p(t) = \frac{E_o I_o}{mL^4} \frac{Q_p(t; \lambda)}{M_p(\lambda)}, \quad p=1, \dots, n_m \quad (7)$$

where $\omega_p(\lambda) = \sqrt{\frac{E_o I_o}{mL^4} \alpha_p^2(\lambda)}$ is the p -th natural frequency of the beam and ζ_p is the modal damping ratio. In addition, the following additional modal parameters $M_p(\lambda)$ and $Q_p(t; \lambda)$ are introduced as follows:

$$Q_p(t; \lambda) = \int_0^1 \phi_p(\xi; \lambda) q(\xi, t) d\xi \quad (8)$$

$$M_p(\lambda) = \int_0^1 \phi_p(\xi; \lambda) \phi_p(\xi; \lambda) d\xi \quad (9)$$

The solution of Eq.(7) can be obtained as the summation of two contributions, related to the free and the forced vibrations, respectively. Both contributions, at least when standard load distributions are considered, can be inferred.

The integration constants appearing in Eq. (3) can be obtained by enforcing the relevant boundary conditions. Without loss of generality, here the case of a pinned-pinned beam is considered, whose boundary conditions are as follows:

$$\phi(0; \lambda) = 0; \quad \phi''(0; \lambda) = 0; \quad \phi(1; \lambda) = 0; \quad \phi''(1; \lambda) = 0 \quad (10)$$

which lead to the following characteristic equation

$$f_{1,r}(1; \lambda) f_{3,r}''(1; \lambda) - f_{3,r}(1; \lambda) f_{1,r}''(1; \lambda) = 0 \quad (11)$$

Once the frequency parameters are numerically computed by Eq. (11), the corresponding four integration constants can be inferred accordingly by solving the system in Eq. (10).

3 EXPLICIT APPROXIMATED APPROACH

An explicit approximated formulation is here proposed to assess the variability of the dynamic response of a damaged beam associated to a non-deterministic parameter in the beam configuration. In particular, the crack severities will be considered as uncertain variables in given intervals $\lambda_i \in [\underline{\lambda}_i, \bar{\lambda}_i]$. A generic value of the i -th crack severity λ_i can be then expressed as:

$$\lambda_i = \lambda_{o,i} + \beta_i \quad (12)$$

with $\beta_i \in [-\Delta\lambda_i, \Delta\lambda_i]$ being $\Delta\lambda_i$ the deviation amplitude.

Let us consider the case of a generic cracked beam with uncertain severities $\lambda = [\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_i, \dots, \lambda_n]$ according to the model introduced in the previous section. In order to provide an approximated evaluation of the main modal parameters of the damaged beam affected by uncertainty in the damage intensities, $2n$ significant damage configurations will be considered, and the correspondence between exact and approximated computations of the considered modal parameters (frequency parameter $\alpha_p^4(\lambda)$, generalized modal mass $M_p(\lambda)$ and load term $Q_p(t; \lambda)$) for such configurations will be enforced. Each of the n pairs of these configurations can be defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\lambda}_s &= [\lambda_{o,1}, \lambda_{o,2}, \dots, \bar{\lambda}_s, \dots, \lambda_{o,n}] \\ \underline{\lambda}_s &= [\lambda_{o,1}, \lambda_{o,2}, \dots, \underline{\lambda}_s, \dots, \lambda_{o,n}] \end{aligned} \quad s = 1, \dots, n \quad (13)$$

The following interpolating formula, proposed by Sherman and Morrison in [12] for the inversion of an invertible matrix and already employed in [13], is adapted for the treated case and here proposed to provide an estimation of the interval frequency parameters as functions of the uncertain damage configuration, as well as the generalized modal mass and the load terms:

$$\alpha_p^4(\lambda) \cong \alpha_{o,p}^4 + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\beta_i a_{p,i}}{1 + \beta_i b_{p,i}} \quad , \quad p = 1, \dots, n_m, \quad \beta_i \in [-\Delta\lambda_i, \Delta\lambda_i] \quad (14)$$

$$M_p(\lambda) \cong M_{o,p} + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\beta_i c_{p,i}}{1 + \beta_i d_{p,i}} \quad , \quad p = 1, \dots, n_m, \quad \beta_i \in [-\Delta\lambda_i, \Delta\lambda_i] \quad (15)$$

$$Q_p(t; \lambda) \cong Q_{o,p}(t) + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\beta_i e_{p,i}(t)}{1 + \beta_i f_{p,i}(t)} \quad , \quad p = 1, \dots, n_m, \quad \beta_i \in [-\Delta\lambda_i, \Delta\lambda_i] \quad (16)$$

being $\alpha_{o,p}^4$, $M_{o,p}$ and $Q_{o,p}(t)$ the p -th modal parameters associated to the nominal damage distribution $\lambda_o = [\lambda_{o,1}, \lambda_{o,2}, \dots, \lambda_{o,n}]$, whereas $a_{p,i}$, $b_{p,i}$, $c_{p,i}$, $d_{p,i}$ and $e_{p,i}(t)$, $f_{p,i}(t)$ represent appropriate sets of coefficients that can be explicitly evaluated following the procedure outlined in what follows based on the solution of a set of nonlinear equations. In particular, without loss of generality, the procedure is presented with reference to the frequency parameter approximation, but it can be also applied to obtain the coefficients for the generalized modal mass and for the load terms too. By enforcing the correspondence between exact and approximated expressions of the frequency parameters for the considered $2n$ damage configurations

$\underline{\lambda}_s, \bar{\lambda}_s, s = 1, \dots, n$ reported in Eq. (13), the n pairs of coefficients $a_{p,s}, b_{p,s}$ assume the following expressions:

$$\begin{aligned} a_{p,s} &= \frac{2}{\Delta\lambda_s} \frac{[\alpha_p^4(\bar{\lambda}_s) - \alpha_{o,p}^4][\alpha_{o,p}^4 - \alpha_p^4(\underline{\lambda}_s)]}{\alpha_p^4(\bar{\lambda}_s) - \alpha_p^4(\underline{\lambda}_s)} \\ b_{p,s} &= \frac{1}{\Delta\lambda_s} \frac{2\alpha_{o,p}^4 - \alpha_p^4(\underline{\lambda}_s) - \alpha_p^4(\bar{\lambda}_s)}{\alpha_p^4(\bar{\lambda}_s) - \alpha_p^4(\underline{\lambda}_s)} \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

$p = 1, \dots, n_m$ and $s = 1, \dots, n$. In Figure 3 the accuracy of the approximated solution is reported for a pinned-pinned cracked beam ($\xi_1 = 0.4$, $\lambda_{o,1} = 0.2$, $\Delta\lambda_1 = 0.2$) subjected to a distributed uniform unit step load $q_0 = 1$ applied on half of the beam. In particular, in Figures 2b, 2d, 2f the comparisons between exact and approximated parameters are shown for the first five frequencies, that is frequency parameters (Figure 2b), generalized modal mass (Figure 2d) and load term (Figure 2f); all the terms are normalized by the corresponding nominal values. The continuous lines correspond to the exact properties, whereas the dashed lines are relative to the approximated solution. In Figure 2c, 2e, 2g the corresponding relative errors are reported.

The subsequent step of the present formulation is to explicitly assess the variability of a generic response term $r(\xi_r, t; \lambda)$ at a desired abscissa ξ_r and, as a particular case, the corresponding bounds within given intervals of the uncertain parameters. A standard procedure would require to compute $r(\xi_r, t; \lambda)$ according to the exact computation for a finite number n_λ of configurations associated to the uncertain parameters λ , for example at given equally spaced steps. This strategy implies the computation of the fundamental frequencies for n_λ times, as well as solving the integrals in Eqs. (8) and (9).

An alternative procedure is to express the response of the beam according to the approximated but explicit formulation reported in the previous section in terms of fundamental frequencies $\alpha_i^4(\lambda)$, generalized masses $M_i(\lambda)$ and load terms $Q_i(\lambda)$. The generic response of the beam can be expressed according to Eq.(6). The mode shapes and their derivatives can be obtained by replacing in Eqs. (3)-(5) the approximated frequency parameter computed according to Eq. (14); the approximated modal coordinates, considering the entire response or only the steady-state response, will require the computation of the modal generalized mass and of the load term according to the scheme proposed in Eqs. (15) and (16).

Under these hypotheses, which require the exact solution of the problem at $2n+1$ given configurations of the damage pattern, namely $\lambda_o; \bar{\lambda}_s, \underline{\lambda}_s, s = 1, \dots, n$, the dependency of the dynamic response on the damage intensities can be explicitly provided. A further resulting important advantage of the proposed procedure lies in the possibility of inferring the bounds of a certain response parameter; to this purpose, from the symbolic response expression, which is function of the damage intensities, the bounds of the response, associated to uncertain but bounded intervals of the damage severities, can be simply obtained by solving two problems of maximum/minimum of constrained nonlinear functions.

4 APPLICATIONS

The final goal of the proposed approach is the exploitation of the explicit expressions for a proper time history analysis considering uncertainties in the damage severities at the cracked

sections. Therefore, the effectiveness of the proposed approximated solution will be in the following assessed by comparing the bounds of the response computed according to a scanning exact procedure with those obtained through the procedure proposed in the previous section.

Figure 2: Comparison between exact and approximated modal properties for a (a) cracked beam: (b) frequency parameter and (c) relative error, (d) generalized modal mass and (e) relative error, (f) load term and (g) relative error

To this purpose, the single cracked beam reported in Figure 2a and subjected to a pulsating distributed load, with intensity $q_0 \sin \omega t$ ($q_0 = 1$, $\omega = 5 \text{ rad/s}$), acting on the left half of the beam is considered. As response parameter, the transversal displacement $u(\xi_r, t; \lambda)$ with $\xi_r = 0.5$ is adopted; in addition, the first five frequencies with an associated damping equal to

0.05 are accounted for. The results are computed according to the set of physical data corresponding to a beam with the following characteristics: $L=5$ m, $E=2.1 \cdot 10^{11}$ N/m², $I= 8.33 \cdot 10^{-6}$ m⁴, $m= 75$ kg/m. In Figure 3 the grey area represents the envelope of the exact responses computed scanning the damage intensities at evenly spaced steps $\Delta \tilde{\lambda}_1 = 0.01$ (in this case 41 exact analyses were run). It is worth to notice that the bounds of the responses cannot be identified at each step considering just the bounds of the crack severity; to find the correct bounds of the response theoretically it would be necessary to run an infinite number of analyses. In Figure 3 the bounds of the response are computed according to the procedure here proposed. Such a procedure requires to compute the exact modal properties for three values of damage severities (namely $\lambda_1 = 0, \lambda_1 = 0.2, \lambda_1 = 0.4$) and then to solve two maximum/minimum conditioned problems for each time step, thus strongly limiting the required computational burden. The relevant lower and upper bounds are reported with the blue dashed and dashdot lines, respectively.

Figure 3. Interval time-domain response for the beam reported in Figure 2a: comparison between the exact results associated to a re-analysis (grey band) and response bounds obtained with the proposed approach.

In the dynamics of structures, a useful tool to summarize the behavior of a structure subjected to frequency-dependent loads is the frequency-response curve. Basically, given a pulsating load with frequency ω applied to a structure, a frequency-response curve collects the magnification factor of the steady-state response with respect to the corresponding static response [14]. In an undamped deterministic analysis the frequency-response curve tends to diverge when ω assumes a value corresponding to each of the natural frequencies of the system (resonance phenomenon); even in presence of damping the peaks of the responses (that do not diverge for damped systems) can be encountered in correspondence of the damped natural frequencies. When an uncertainty in the damage severity of cracks in a beam is considered, the natural frequencies can change significantly; therefore, it is expected that an interval frequency-response band will show that the bounds of the response can be associated to values of the damage severities which do not coincide with the bounds of the considered interval.

To this purpose a further application is here proposed with reference to the double-cracked beam reported in Figure 4a, computing the frequency-response interval spectrum. The considered beam is a pinned-pinned double cracked one subjected to a concentrated pulsating load acting on the midpoint of the beam, $q(\xi, t) = P_o \delta(\xi - \xi_L) \sin \omega t$ ($P_o = 1$, $\xi_L = 0.5$, $\omega = 10$ rad/s). The two cracks are located at $\xi_1 = 0.2$ and $\xi_2 = 0.7$, respectively, and are both characterized by the nominal intensity $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = 0.05$. The approximated modal parameters are

computed considering an interval amplitude $\Delta\lambda_1 = \Delta\lambda_2 = 0.05$. The results depicted in Figure 4 are relative to the damped system with damping equal to 0.05 for all the three considered frequencies. In Figures 4b and 4c, together with the grey area representing the envelope of the response obtained through re-analysis (considering 121 exact analyses associated to damage severity steps $\Delta\tilde{\lambda}_1 = \Delta\tilde{\lambda}_2 = 0.01$), as a function of the frequency ratio $\eta(\lambda) = \alpha_\omega^2 / \alpha_1^2(\lambda) = \omega / \omega_1(\lambda)$.

Figures 4c and 4d show that the proposed approach, even exhibiting a reduced precision with respect to the previous applications, at least in the central range of the frequency ratio ($7 \leq \eta \leq 12$), leads to conservative results, that is it never underestimates the actual response variability of the dynamic response.

Figure 4. Frequency-response interval spectrum for the beam reported in (a): comparison between the exact results associated to a re-analysis (grey band) and (b) response bounds obtained with the proposed approach; (c) analogous results for the normalized response.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, taking advantage of the Sherman and Morrison formula, an explicit approximated solution of the main modal parameters (namely eigenfrequencies generalized modal mass and load term) of a multi-cracked beam subjected to external load, is proposed. Such formulas explicitly account for a variability of the crack severities. The proposed expressions are able to provide a good approximation of the modal parameters and require their exact computation only for a limited number of damage configurations. The proposed strategy allows addressing both direct and inverse problems. After an extensive validation in terms of modal parameters, the dynamic response of cracked beams is evaluated both in time and frequency domains and, given the range of variability of the damage severities, the bounds of the response are identified and compared to those associated to a re-analysis. In particular, it is shown that such response bounds can be associated to damage configurations which do not correspond to bounds of the considered damage intensity range, thus demonstrating the unsuitability of the convex analysis for dynamic problems in presence of uncertain damage severities. The proposed explicit solution seems to provide promising results and its exploitation for other dynamic problems could be explored in the future.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support of the Ministero dell'Istruzione, dell'Università e della Ricerca (National Research Project PRIN 2015JW9NJT “Advanced mechanical modeling of new materials and structures for the solution of 2020 Horizon challenges”).

REFERENCES

- [1] ENV 1991-1, Eurocode 1-Basis of Design and Actions on Structures-Part 1: Basis of Design, 1994.
- [2] G.R. Irwin, Analysis of stresses and strains near the end of a crack traversing a plate. *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, **24**, 361-364, 1957.
- [3] S.A. Paipetis, A.D. Dimarogonas, *Analytical Methods in Rotor Dynamics*, Elsevier Applied Science, London, 1986.
- [4] F. Cannizzaro, A. Greco, S. Caddemi, I. Calì, Closed form solutions of a multi-cracked circular arch under static loads. *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, **121**(15), 191-200, 2017.
- [5] S. Caddemi, I. Calì, F. Cannizzaro, Influence of an elastic end support on the dynamic stability of Beck's column with multiple weak sections. *International Journal of Nonlinear Mechanics*, **69**, 14-28, 2015.
- [6] N. Impollonia, G. Ricciardi, Explicit solutions in the stochastic dynamics of structural systems. *Probabilistic Engineering Mechanics*, **21**, 171-181, 2006.
- [7] D. Moens, D. Vandepitte, Fuzzy Finite Element Method for Frequency Response Function Analysis of Uncertain Structures. *AIAA Journal*, **40**(1), 126-136, 2002.
- [8] G. Alefeld, J. Herzberger, *Introduction to interval computation*, Academic press, 1984.
- [9] J. Hu, Z. Qiu, Non-probabilistic convex models and interval analysis method for dynamic response of a beam with bounded uncertainty. *Applied Mathematical Modelling*, **34**(3), 725-734, 2010.
- [10] F. Cannizzaro, J. De Los Rios, S. Caddemi, I. Calì, S. Ilanko, On the use of a roving body with rotary inertia to locate cracks in beams. *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, **425**(7), 275-300, 2018.
- [11] C. Bilello, *Theoretical and experimental investigation on damaged beams under moving systems*, Ph.D. Thesis, University of Palermo, Italy, 2001.
- [12] J. Sherman, W.J. Morrison, Adjustment of an Inverse Matrix Corresponding to Changes in the Elements of a Given Column or a Given Row of the Original Matrix (abstract), *Annals of Mathematical Statistics*, **20**, 621, 1949.
- [13] N. Impollonia, A method to derive approximate explicit solutions for structural mechanics problems. *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, **43**, 7082-7098, 2006.
- [14] A.K. Chopra, *Dynamics of Structures, Theory and Application to Earthquake Engineering*. Upper Saddle River: Prentice Hall, 2001.